

Index of Training material

Multivariate integration of multi-omics data with mixOmics

6 March 2024

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Multivariate integration of multi-omics data with mixOmics	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/5XpmQ5X89IA
Mixomics_Bioccommons	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record